

Note on the distribution of *Salamandra salamandra cf. bernardezi* in Asturias, northern Spain

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INTRODUCTION

The subspecies *Salamandra salamandra bernardezi* is commonly found in the provinces of Asturias, Galicia, and Cantabria in the north of Spain. This form of Fire Salamander is relatively small and slender with a rounded, blunt snout. The colour pattern is generally composed of bright to dull yellow dorsolateral stripes. Interestingly, the females of some populations of this subspecies give birth to completely metamorphosed juveniles. The typical *bernardezi* phenotype was described from the city of Oviedo (WOLTERSTORFF, 1928). Later, populations of small and atypically coloured animals (referred to in this paper as 'cf. *bernardezi*') were described from the river Tendi (BARIO & FONOLL, 1997) and the river

Marea valleys east of Oviedo (PASMANS & KELLER, 2000). In order to examine the distribution of these aberrant populations, the areas neighbouring the river Tendi and Marea valleys were visited in July 1998, April 1999 and May 2002, and the phenotypes of local fire salamanders were noted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The localities at which *S. s. cf. bernardezi* was found, and the suggested distribution range, are summarised in Fig. 1. A tendency was noted toward reduction of the salamander's yellow coloration in the north-eastern portion of this area. The most 'typical' cf. *bernardezi* animals were found in the area limited by two rivers: the river Piloña and the river Sella. These include animals from the Tendi river valley and the Sierra de Faces. At both these localities and in the Sierra de Giblianiella and the river Marea valley, salamanders were only found from about five kilometres upstream of the mouth of the respective rivers in the river Piloña. In the river Marea valley, a strong tendency was noticed towards loss of the typical striped pattern downstream, resulting in typical river Marea salamanders as described by PASMANS & KELLER (2000). This phenomenon was not noticed in the Tendi valley. Remarkably, a typical '*bernardezi*' animal was found high up the slopes of the neighbouring southern river valley, merely two kilometres from the most upstream locality in the Tendi valley at which typical cf. *bernardezi* salamanders were found. Typical *bernardezi* from Oviedo (GÜNTHER,

View on the Sierra de Faces, April 2002.

Photo: F. Pasmans

1996) and from Picos de Europa (SCHMIDT, 2001) show some tendency toward abnormal colour patterns; brown and even red animals being fairly common. Genetic founder effect and subsequent very poor genetic exchange might cause the extreme concentration of these odd-coloured animals in the Piloña-Sella area. Although nowadays no apparent barriers exist between these populations and the more southern, typically coloured populations, these salamanders might have been effectively separated during the last ice age, and restricted to the lower parts of the valleys. Indeed, the gradual increase of abnormally coloured animals in the Marea valley downstream might support this hypothesis, suggesting recent genetic exchange, thus enhancing heterozygosity and hence a re-establishment of the typical *bernardezi* patterns. These populations could certainly provide rewarding material for future studies.

Fig 1. Schematic distribution map showing the localities at which *Salamandra salamandra* cf. *bernardezi* was found in Asturias, northern Spain. Three colour morphs were differentiated: typical Ovedo-like animals (☆), salamanders which exhibit strong expansion of the yellow markings (Δ) and salamanders that show a high tendency towards reduction of the yellow markings (▲).

Adult *Salamandra salamandra* cf. *bernardezi* with reduction of yellow markings, Sierra de Faces.

Photo: F. Pasmans

Adult *Salamandra salamandra* cf. *bernardezi* with typical Oviedo colour pattern.

Photo: F. Pasmans

SUMMARY

Two populations of atypically coloured morphs of *Salamandra salamandra* cf. *bernardezi* were known to inhabit two river valleys in northeast Asturias, Spain. In this study, the phenotype of animals from adjacent areas was determined, resulting in a preliminary distribution map.

Adult *Salamandra salamandra* cf. *bernardezi* with expansion of yellow markings, Rio Marea.

Photo: F. Pasmans

LITERATURE

- BARRIO, L.B. & R. FONOLL, 1997. Sobre una población de salamandras *Salamandra salamandra* con pigmentación anómala. Bol. Assoc. Herpetol. Esp. 8: 33-36.
- GÜNTHER, E., 1996. *Salamandra salamandra bernardezi* Wolterstorff, 1928 in Oviedo, Spanien: Ein Schwanzlurch als Stadtbewohner. Zeitschr. Feldherpetol. 3: 1-18.
- PASMANS, F. & H. KELLER, 2000. Morphological variation in neighbouring populations of *Salamandra salamandra bernardezi* in northern Spain. Zeitschr. Feldherpetol. 7: 77-84.
- SCHMIDT, H., 2001. Bemerkungen zur Fortpflanzungsbiologie und zu den Farbvarianten von *Salamandra salamandra bernardezi*. herpetofauna 23: 19-22.
- WOLTERSTORFF, W., 1928. Vollmolch-gebärende Feuersalamander aus Oviedo. Blätt. Aquar.-Terrar.-Kde. 39: 132-133.